

A New Constant for Fixed Oils. Hypochlorous Acid Value.

BY M. GOSWAMI AND K. L. BASU

In a preliminary note on the subject (*Analyst*, 1934, 59, 533) the authors indicated the possibility of determining the unsaturation of fixed oils by means of hypochlorous acid,* which is a distinct improvement on the present methods of doing the same in many respects, especially in respect of time factor ; this being observed very carefully in other methods to avoid substitution. There were preliminary difficulties, *e.g.*, interference of alcohol, indicator, stability of sodium hypochlorite solution, etc., and after numerous experiments the following method has been standardised.

The oil or fat is saponified with alcoholic potash, the excess of KOH neutralised by HCl, alcohol driven off and the soap is diluted with water ; a dilute solution of sodium hypochlorite of known strength is then added and the whole acidified with calculated amount of dilute H₂SO₄ (to liberate the whole of hypochlorous acid) and kept for 5 to 15 minutes. After absorption the excess of HOCl is then determined by adding KI solution and titrating the liberated iodine. The calculated and theoretical values as deduced from Iodine values are found to agree very fairly even within the time factor of 2 hours. The additional advantages of this process are the following :—

- (1) The saponification value is determined simultaneously without recourse to second weighing.
- (2) Time required for complete saturation is only 5 to 15 minutes.
- (3) Before determining the value one need not know whether the oil or fat is drying, semi-drying or non-drying as is required in ordinary methods.

* It was thought that the oils would absorb the acid like CH₂=CH₂ in the following way :—

and there would be no substitution and therefore no question of time factor.

EXPERIMENTAL.

NaOCl solution (5 c.c., prepared from bleaching powder solution and Na_2CO_3 , containing slight excess of Na_2CO_3 and approximately of the strength 5 c.c. = 20–25 c.c. of $\frac{N}{10}$ $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$) and excess of KI solution are taken in a conical flask and acidified with H_2SO_4 (dil.), the iodine liberated is titrated with thiosulphate and the experiment is repeated with standard H_2SO_4 solution, the volume of the latter required to liberate just the full amount of iodine from the solution is thus determined.*

0.120-0-125 G. of oil is saponified in the usual way with 25 c.c. of approx. $N/5$ alcoholic KOH. The excess of the alkali is exactly neutralised with standard HCl using bromothymol blue as indicator. The alcohol is then evaporated off on the water-bath until a pasty mass remains. The soap is dissolved in water, transferred to a 750 c.c. flask and the solution diluted to 600 c.c. To this 5 c.c. of NaOCl solution is added followed by H_2SO_4 of known strength just to neutralise the free Na_2CO_3 and to liberate HOCl from the hypochlorite. The flask is quickly closed by means of a rubber stopper fitted with a dropping funnel containing KI solution, well stirred and kept in a dark and cool place for 5-15 mins. The KI solution in the funnel is then blown in and the flask well shaken. The dropping funnel is then washed and taken out. The solution is now acidified with excess of H_2SO_4 solution and the iodine liberated is titrated against standard thiosulphate. Blank experiment is done side by side. The difference in the thiosulphate figures gives the amount of HOCl absorbed (1 c.c. of N -thiosulphate = 0.002625 g. of HOCl).

* From the reactions :

the amounts of H_2SO_4 required to neutralise respectively Na_2CO_3 of the hypochlorous solution, to liberate HOCl and to neutralise KOH of equation (c) are determined. For example in a particular experiment 5 c.c. of NaOCl = 22.6 c.c. of 0.9819N/10-thio. and 3.25 c.c. of 0.9313N- H_2SO_4 is required to liberate iodine completely. Now 22.6 c.c. of 0.9819 N/10-thio. corresponds to 0.8268 g. of NaOCl and to liberate HOCl from this amount of the hypochlorite 1.192 c.c. of H_2SO_4 of the above strength is required whilst the same volume is necessary for KOH. Thus (3.25-2.384) i.e. 0.866 c.c. of 0.9313 N- H_2SO_4 is required for the neutralisation of the excess of Na_2CO_3 present in the hypochlorite solution. These calculations are necessary for knowing the exact amount of H_2SO_4 required for Na_2CO_3 and for NaOCl,

TABLE I.

Blank experiments performed for standardising the method.

Water added = 600 c.c. Vol. of NaOCl soln. = 5 c.c.

Expt.	Time ¹ .	H ₂ SO ₄ (0.9313N).	Indicator used.	Thiosulphate (0.9819N) required.
1	2 hrs.	2.05 c.c. ²	Nil	22.15 c.c.
2	2 hrs.	3.25 ³	Nil ⁴	22.15
3	30 mins.	2.05 ²	Phenolphthalein	19.95
4	2 hrs.	2.05 ²	Bromothymol blue ⁵	22.15
5	2 hrs.	3.25 ³	„	22.15

¹ Time after which titration is made. ² Amount required just to neutralise Na₂CO₃ and to decompose NaOCl.

³ Whole amount to liberate I₂ completely.

⁴ 1 % sol.—2 drs. ⁵ 1 % sol.—2 drs.

From the above experiments it is clear that phenolphthalein cannot be used as indicator after saponification for neutralisation of the excess of KOH and that bromothymol blue can safely be used. Interference of alcohol has also been investigated.

TABLE II.

Water added = 600 c.c. Thiosulphate required (blank) = 22.15 c.c. NaOCl soln. = 5 c.c.

Expt.	Time.	H ₂ SO ₄ (0.9313N).	Alcohol.	Thio (0.9819N).
6	2 hrs.	* 2.05 c.c.	25 c.c.	20.1 c.c.
7	„	† 3.25	„	20.70
8	„	* 2.05	10	21.0
9	30 mins.	„	10	21.25
10	2 hrs.	„	5	21.4
11	30 mins.	„	5	21.55
12	2 hrs.	† 3.25	10	21.6
13	30 mins.	„	10	22.00
14	2 hrs.	† 3.25	5	21.65
15	30 mins.	„	5	22.15

* Amount just to neutralise Na₂CO₃ and to liberate HOCl from NaOCl completely.

† Whole amount of acid to liberate the I₂ completely.

Experiments Nos. 6-15 in Table II show that as the amount of alcohol decreases the thiosulphate figures approach the blank ones. Again when the whole amount of the acid is added the difference between the titration figures is smaller than when the exact amount of the acid (required for Na_2CO_3 and NaOCl) is added. The following experiments were done with pure sodium oleate using bromothymol blue as indicator showing that the soap absorbs HOCl .

TABLE III.

Water added = 600 c.c. Vol. of NaOCl soln. = 5 c.c. Na -oleate soln. = 20 c.c.

Expt.	Time.	H_2SO_4 (0.9313N).	Thio. (0.9819N).	Blank thio without oleate.	Alcohol used.
16	2 hrs.	*2.05	12.80 c.c.	22.15 c.c.	Nil
17	„	†3.25	12.45
18	„	*2.05	12.3	21.00	10 c.c.
19	„	†3.25	12.15	21.60	„
20	„	*2.05	12.15	20.1	25
21	„	*3.25	12.15	20.70	..

* Amount just to neutralise Na_2CO_3 and to liberate HOCl from NaOCl completely.

† Amount to liberate I_2 completely.

Experiments Nos. 16-21 in Table III show that the whole amount of acid cannot be added when there is no alcohol. To get the best result the alcohol should be evaporated off after saponification.

In the following experiments with oils, the alcohol, after saponification value is determined, is evaporated off on the water-bath (the soap remaining as a pasty mass) and the acid (0.9313 N- H_2SO_4) is added just to neutralise the free Na_2CO_3 of the hypochlorite solution and to decompose NaOCl to HOCl . Iodine values by Wiji's method are determined simultaneously. These and the corresponding HOCl values (% of HOCl absorbed) as calculated from the latter are given for comparison in the tables.

Non-drying Oils.

TABLE IV.

Ground-nut oil.

I_2 value = 87.6. NaOCl soln. = 5 c.c. (= 22.6 c.c. of thio. used).
Corresponding HOCl value (called henceforward H. C. value) = 18.09.

Wt. of oil.	Time.	Thio (0.9819N)	Blank thio.	Diff. thio.	HOCl absorbed.
0.1502 g.	15 mins.	11.50 c.c.	22.0 c.c.	10.50 c.c.	18.02 %
0.1598	1 hr.	11.20	22.05	10.85	17.5
0.1672	2 hrs.	10.50	22.0	11.50	17.73
*0.1534	5 mins.	12.05	22.0	9.95	16.72
*0.0864	5 „	16.15	22.05	5.9	17.6

* Shows that the absorption is not complete within 5 minutes with more than 0.15 g. of the oil.

Buffalo ghee (butter fat).

NaOCl soln. = 7.5 c.c. (= 26.15 c.c. of thio used).

Iodine value = 35.4. Corresponding H. C. value = 7.313.

Wt. of oil.	Time.	Thio N/10.	Blank thio.	Diff. thio.	HOCl absorbed.
0.1336 g.	2 hrs.	21.55 c.c.	25.50 c.c.	3.95 c.c.	7.76 %
0.1822	1 hr.	20.5	25.70	5.2	7.49
0.1414	15 mins	21.5	25.7	4.2	7.796

Cocanut oil.

NaOCl soln. = 7.5 c.c. (= 26.0 c.c. of thio used).

Iodine value = 9. Corresponding H. C. value = 1.859.

Wt. of oil.	Time.	Thio (0.988N/10).	Blank thio.	Diff. thio.	HOCl absorbed.
0.1501 g.	2 hrs.	24.5 c.c.	25.6 c.c.	1.1 c.c.	1.9 %
0.1560	1 hr.	24.45	25.75	1.3	2.16
0.1480	15 mins.	24.65	25.75	1.10	1.928

TABLE IV (continued).

NaOCl soln. = 7.5 c.c. (= 26.0 c.c. of thio. used).

Olive oil.

Iodine value = 88 Corresponding H. C. value = 18.18.

Wt. of oil.	Time.	Thio (0.988N/10).	Blank thio.	Diff. thio.	HOCl (absorbed)
0.1736 g.	2 hrs.	13.40	25.6	12.2	18.2
0.1627	1 hr.	14.55	25.7	11.15	17.77
0.1081	15 mins	18.35	25.7	7.35	17.64

Semi-drying Oils.

TABLE V.

Mustard oil.

Iodine value = 108. Corresponding H. C. value = 22.31.

0.1218 g.	2 hrs.	15.15	25.6	10.45	22.25 %
0.1073	1 hr.	16.15	25.6	9.45	22.84
0.1161	15 mins.	15.7	25.7	10.00	22.34

Sesame oil.

Iodine value = 110. Corresponding H. C. value = 22.73.

0.1281 g.	2 hrs.	14.5	25.6	11.1	22.48 %
0.1085	15 mins.	16.50	25.75	9.25	22.11
0.1235	1 hr.	14.95	25.7	10.75	22.57

Drying and Fish Oils.

TABLE VI.

Linseed oil.

Iodine value = 185. Corresponding H. C. value = 38.22.

0.1836 g.	2 hrs.	7.4 c.c.	25.6 c.c.	18.2 c.c.	35.33 %
0.0974	1 hr.	12.60	25.7	13.1	34.88
0.0861	15 mins.	14.05	25.7	11.65	35.10

Clupea ilisha oil.

Iodine value = 88. Corresponding H. C. value = 18.18.

0.1068 g.	2 hrs.	18.2	25.6	7.4	17.97
0.1005	1 hr.	18.8	25.7	6.9	17.80
0.0948	15 mins.	19.2	25.7	6.5	17.78

SUMMARY.

1. The method consists of the determination of percentage of absorption of HOCl by sodium salts of the fatty acids present in oils after saponification value is determined with bromothymol blue as indicator.

2. The technique of the process depends upon careful manipulation of the amount of sulphuric acid added just to liberate HOCl from NaOCl solution which is added to the soap solution and to neutralise free Na_2CO_3 .

3. The alcohol used for the determination of saponification value need not be removed completely; soap thus obtained is then dissolved in water and treated with NaOCl.

4. Theoretical and calculated H. C. values agree very fairly.

5. Simultaneous determinations of saponification value and the degree of unsaturation are possible by the present method without recourse to second weighing.

6. Absorption is complete in 5–15 minutes with 0.15 g. of substance.

7. Time factor does not vitiate the result to any appreciable extent.

8. No preliminary sorting of oils as non-drying, semi-drying and drying is necessary as is required in other methods.

DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA.

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